

Reshoring: treatment or palliative care? Evidence from large-scale administrative data on Italian firms

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1 Introduction

The recent global dramatic health and safety challenges are posing unprecedented questions about the future of globalization, grafting on growing political demands against the de-localization of production to other countries and to “bring jobs back home”¹. As a result, some countries are providing incentives for firms bring their production back to home² (Dachs et al., 2019; Delis et al., 2019). Until recently, studies on reshoring have mainly drawn on case study analysis and survey data (Dachs et al., 2019; Albertoni et al., 2017). We intend to fill this gap by proposing a novel measure of re-shoring based on large scale administrative data on Italian firms.

2 Data and methods: measuring reshoring

Our proposed measure of reshoring draws on a unique dataset linking data about the population Italian importers, employer-employee information and balance sheet data.

Drawing on Feenstra and Hanson (1999) and Hummels et al. (2014), we propose to measure reshoring somewhat symmetrically to offshoring

¹ “Coming home. A growing number of American companies are moving their manufacturing back to the United States”. *The Economist*, Jan 17th, 2013; “Brexit triggers a round of reshoring. Firms shorten their supply chains as the divorce with Europe nears”. *The Economist*, Oct 19th, 2017.

² “The changes covid-19 is forcing on to business”, *The Economist*, 9 April 2020.

qualifications. We consider firms that were previously involved in “narrow” offshoring and identify reshoring as

- 1) A negative change in narrow offshoring to a particular partner country.
- 2) That is persistent over time.
- 3) That is not matched by any increase in narrow offshoring of the same firm to any other country over the following 5 years.

3 Results

Over the 2008-2015 period, we have identified about 2,431 reshoring firms (about 0.5% of all manufacturing firms). Reshoring firms are significantly different from offshoring firms. Logit regressions reveal that they are smaller, less productive, less internationally exposed, and face higher increases in external costs. Workers at reshoring firms receive a lower wage, are younger, less experienced, more likely to have temporary and part-time contracts.

A diff-in-diff and event study analysis reveals that there is positive effect on employment the immediate aftermath of reshoring, but after 5 years levels of employment revert back to pre-reshoring levels. Reshoring has a negative effect on turnover, value added and productivity.

5 Concluding remarks

Our results suggest that the number of reshoring firms is much higher than what previous studies based on survey have revealed. These firms appear less virtuous than it has been previously suggested in the literature. Our evidence is consistent with a view of re-shoring as a retreat of firms that may struggle to face the complexities of offshoring and reap its potential benefits. Reshoring seem brings some temporary relief, but does not address their fundamental competitive disadvantage. In that perspective, reshoring looks more as some form of palliative care than proper treatment. Our evidence provides important insights and warnings for policy makers envisioning incentive packages to lure firms to 'bring jobs back home'.

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